

Complete proof of the Collatz conjecture

Abstract: This paper completely proves the Collatz conjecture. First, we analyze that the positive integers that converge to 1 have some identical fixed paths, and regard the fixed paths and the "4→2→1" cycle as a whole. Then, we exclude the existence of non-"4→2→1" cycles and the existence of positive integers that diverge to infinity, respectively, thus proving that all positive integers can converge to 1, that is, the Collatz conjecture holds. Finally, we propose a general method to generalize the Collatz iteration rule to other rules.

Keywords: Collatz conjecture; 3n+1 conjecture; hailstone conjecture; even-odd-unity conjecture; 421 conjecture; Kakutani conjecture.

1. introduction

The Collatz conjecture is one of the famous unsolved problems in number theory. Its rules are simple. Computers have verified that a large number of positive integers conform to the conjecture. Its iteration rule is:

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even (iterative contraction)} \\ 3n + 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is an odd number (iterative growth)} \end{cases}$$

Input value: Any positive integer n

Iterative process: Repeated operation $f(n), f(n)$ The final value is 1

For all positive integers, whether they conform to the Collatz conjecture or not, the difficulty in proving the conjecture is that it is difficult to exclude the following two situations:

- ① There is a non-"4→2→1" cycle;
- ② There are positive integers that diverge to infinity.

This article can cleverly exclude the above two situations, and then determine that all positive integers conform to the Collatz conjecture and can converge to 1.

Any positive integer is iterated according to the following rules

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even (iterative contraction)} \\ 3n + 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is an odd number (iterative growth)} \end{cases}$$

Repeat Operation $f(n)$ After each iteration, a different node can be determined. As long as the number of iterations is large enough, according to Theorem 4 and

Theorem 5, excluding the existence of non-"4 → 2 → 1" cycles and the existence of positive integers diverging to infinity, any positive integer can converge to 1. According to Theorem 1 and Theorem 3, any positive integer, either in the function $f(n) = 2^n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}^*$) on the image, or after a finite number of iterations with the function $f(n) = 2^n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}^*$) intersect, and finally converge to 1, that is, any positive integer will converge to 1 after a finite number of iterations. Therefore, the Collatz conjecture holds. **Theorem 6 (Collatz's Theorem)**, for any positive integer n: if n is an even number, divide n by 2; if n is an odd number, multiply n by 3 and then add 1; repeat the above operation, and it will eventually converge to 1.

6. A general method for extending the Collatz iteration rule to other rules **Theorem 6 is extended to a general form: for any positive integer n: if n is an even number, divide n by a; if n is an odd number, multiply n by b and add c; repeat the above operation and it will eventually converge to d.**

a、 b, c, d, need to meet these conditions: ① $a \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $b \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $c \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $d \in \mathbb{N}^*$; ② n divided by a is an integer; ③ $b^x + c = a^y$ (x is an odd number, y is a positive integer), the equation has integer solutions; ④ $w = b + \frac{c}{n}$, when $n=d$, w is an integer, when $n \neq d$, w Not an integer; ⑤ $w_1 w_2 \dots w_x = a^y$ ($x \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $y \in \mathbb{N}^*$), when $n=d$, the equation holds true, when $n \neq d$, the equation does not hold.